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**PROBLEMS OF FUNCTIONING OF AGRICULTURAL ENTERPRISES OF
UKRAINE IN CONDITIONS OF UNCERTAINTY OF THE BUSINESS
ENVIRONMENT**

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Abstract. The article considers the problems of the functioning of agricultural enterprises in conditions of uncertainty. The main challenges and risks faced by agricultural enterprises are analysed, and possible anti-crisis management measures aimed at minimising losses, responding promptly to challenges and adapting to them are considered.

Keywords: agricultural enterprises, uncertainty, risks, military aggression, anticrisis management

Introduction. In the current environment of constant change and uncertainty, Ukraine's agricultural sector faces numerous challenges to its operation and development: political and economic instability, territorial losses, environmental issues, climate change, and technological and human resource uncertainty. All this forces agricultural enterprises to adapt their strategies, introduce new technologies and find new markets to remain competitive. At the same time, however, risks and costs are rising, making long-term planning and sustainable development of the industry more difficult.

The aim of the study. Highlight the main challenges and risks faced by agricultural enterprises in an uncertain business environment and identify ways to adapt and strategies that will contribute to the industry's competitiveness.

Material and methods. The theoretical and methodological basis of the study were the works of domestic and foreign scholars, leading scientists and practitioners in the field of functioning of enterprises under conditions of uncertainty.

The research used several general scientific and special methods. In particular, the method of system analysis for a detailed understanding of the concept of uncertainty in the context of the functioning of agricultural enterprises, as well as for analysing the main risks; abstract and logical method for substantiating and presenting conclusions and proposals regarding a set of crisis management measures for the effective functioning of agricultural enterprises in conditions of uncertainty.

Results. The current business environment is characterised by a growing level of uncertainty in both the internal and external environment, which poses a serious threat to the stable development of agricultural enterprises. In the face of such unpredictable changes, the key issue is to assess the nature of the risks faced by enterprises and their ability to withstand these risks. Adequate strategies for assessing and adapting to these uncertainties are an important aspect of ensuring the long-term sustainability and development of an enterprise.

As noted by Sokolova Liudmyla (2010) in her scientific works, «...uncertainty is associated with incomplete and inaccurate information about elements of the business environment, random changes in economic activity, unfavourable, in this case force majeure, falling prices in the market, etc. The concept of risk as a possibility, the probability of unfavourable situations, the manifestation of which is losses and expenses, is connected with uncertainty» [1, p. 42].

In addition to this, Sarai Nataliia (2016) notes that «the more complex and uncertain the socio-economic environment is, the more urgent is the need to take into account risk, build and improve adequate tools for its analysis, accounting, modelling and forecasting» [2, p. 35].

Accordingly, we can determine that the existence of agricultural enterprises in conditions of uncertainty is, first of all, the ability to constantly find a balance between risks and opportunities, which requires a clear and qualitative assessment of risk factors and the implementation of measures to minimise them. Uncertainty in the business

environment necessitates rapid adaptation of enterprises to new conditions, including flexibility of management decisions, forecasting possible negative scenarios and building a strategy for dealing with force majeure situations. In the context of the agricultural sector, this means not only responding to market fluctuations but also to unpredictable climate change and regulatory restrictions, which create additional challenges for the sustainable development of enterprises.

At the same time, it should be understood that the Ukrainian agricultural sector is currently facing the task of not only counteracting common challenges and risks, but also developing new approaches to business management and organisation due to active military operations in part of the territory. Therefore, it is necessary to take into account the main risks related to employee safety, asset protection, crop preservation and logistical difficulties. In addition, the threats associated with disruption of supply of resources, damage to infrastructure, as well as possible changes in domestic and foreign markets that require a flexible approach to management and adaptation to new business conditions should be assessed (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. The main risks of Ukrainian agricultural enterprises caused by military aggression

Source: compiled by the author based on data from [3]

Considering all of the above, we understand that agricultural enterprises in the face of uncertainty and constant change need to apply crisis management, which will allow them to respond quickly to unforeseen circumstances, minimise losses and maintain stability in the face of economic, political and environmental instability. Such management includes the following measures: development of crisis scenarios, diversification of risks, increase of resource efficiency and active adaptation to new conditions, which will result in more sustainable operation of enterprises in the long term.

Conclusion. Ukraine's agricultural sector requires fundamental management changes, and the development of effective anti-crisis programmes aimed at improving existing sustainable development strategies, timely and efficient response, and reducing the impact of threats on efficiency and competitiveness, taking into account the current military situation.

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